

Additional information on the masked crab spider *Thomisus blandus* Karsch, 1880 from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae)

Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman¹ & Wynand Uys²

¹DSI/NRF Chair in Biodiversity Value and Change, University of Venda (dippenaaransie@gmail.com);

²Environmental Consultant, Hoedspruit (wynand@ottersden.co.za)

ABSTRACT: The male of *Thomisus blandus* was described from South Africa by Karsch (1880) 145 years ago. The female was only described 18 years later by Pocock (1898) from Escourt. This species is now recorded throughout Africa and Yemen. It has a wide distribution throughout South Africa and is found on trees, grass, herbs and flowers. Different colour variations were observed in females. Additional information on their behaviour, distribution, and conservation in South Africa is provided.

INTRODUCTION

Numerous Thomisidae specimens were sampled during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015), and 38 genera represented by 143 species are known from South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022). The southern African species of the genus *Thomisus* Walckenaer, 1805, were revised by Dippenaar-Schoeman (1983), and specimens from 12 African countries were available for the study.

The first masked crab spider, *Thomisus blandus*, was described from South Africa by Karsch (1880) from a male, but no exact locality data was provided. Eighteen years later, Pocock (1898) added the description of the female (then *T. anthobius*) from KwaZulu-Natal. Several species resembling *T. blandus* were described from countries in Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2025), resulting in five *Thomisus* species and subspecies being synonymised with *T. blandus* (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983). Although large numbers of *T. blandus* were collected during SANSA surveys, little is known about them. Based on live photographs, information on their general morphology and variation of both sexes is provided with notes on their lifestyle, distribution and conservation status.

METHODS

Voucher specimens sampled during SANSA surveys are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at Pretoria Agricultural Research Council (ARC). SANSA requested photographs of spiders for the SANSA Virtual Museum (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012). Additional information was extracted from pictures taken by the public and deposited in iNaturalist, which were downloaded from <https://inaturalist> on May 17, 2025.

Figures 1–5. *Thomisus blandus*. 1. Female dorsal view, with brown abdominal patches. 2. The eye region showing the distinct black marking in the female. 3. Female showing the abdomen decorated with black patches. 4. Male dorsal view. 5. Male anterior view. Credits: 1–2. Wynand Uys. 3. Charissa de Lange. 4–5. Peter Webb.

Figures 6–10. *Thomisus blandus*. 6–7. Eye pattern. 8–9. Epigyne. 10. Palp. Credits. 6. After Comellini (1957). 7. Wynand Uys. 8. Pocock (1898). 9–10. Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983.

TAXONOMY

Thomisus blandus Karsch, 1880

Thomisus blandus Karsch, 1880: 382 (m); Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983: 13 (mf, Synonym of *Thomisus anthobius* Pocock, 1898, *T. a. alboirroratus* (Comellini, 1957), *T. a. delesserti* Caporiacco, 1949, *T. a. ocellitibiis* Caporiacco, 1949, and *T. sus* Strand, 1907; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010: 1066–1067; Dippenaar-Schoeman 2023: 262; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020: 42–43.

Diagnosis: Female: Size: 8.1-9.0 mm; carapace: translucent white (Figs 11 & 14) to fawn (Figs 12 & 13) in live specimens (fawn in alcohol specimens) to yellow (Figs 15); cephalic region with broad mediolateral dark bands in some (Figs 13 & 14), reduced (Fig. 1) or absent in other (Figs 11, 12, 15). Dark, distinct triangular pattern between front eyes (Figs 2, 6-7). But in some specimens the markings are reddish (Fig. 17) or central area are reddish (Fig. 18). Abdomen with distinct abdominal humps; vary from white (Fig. 3) to cream (Fig. 13) to yellow (Fig. 15); lateral sides either without markings or with brown (Fig. 1) or black (Fig. 11) patches that usually are also present dorsally. Leg colour like carapace, translucent (Fig. 13) or suffused with white (Fig. 12); some front legs are decorated with black spots; metatarsi and tarsi with bands, varying between specimens. Epigynum on elevated plate; intromittent orifices in sub-circular pits, separated by broad median septum (Figs 8 & 9).

Male: Size: 2.9-3.6 mm; carapace: dark brown suffused with paler markings (Fig. 4) abdomen yellow to orange-brown with distinct abdominal tubercles; legs: brown similar to carapace, except basal half of all femora which are translucent white; all leg joints white, metatarsi III and IV banded with white (Figs 19 & 20); tarsi III palp dark (Fig. 5); embolus thin, semi-circular; retrolateral tibial apophysis large; tibia pro laterally with numerous scattered strong tubercles bearing setae (Fig. 10).

HABITAT

The species was collected from trees, grass, herbs and flowers. It has also been sampled from crops such as citrus, cotton (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1999), maize, papaya, pumpkin and strawberries (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013).

With the SANSa surveys, it has been sampled from the Fynbos (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2025), Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013) and Savanna (Foord *et al.*, 2011) biomes. It was mainly absent from the arid biomes.

Figures 11–21. *Thomisus blandus*. 11–18. Showing the variation in shape and colour found in females. 19–21. Showing two adult and one immature male. Credits: 11 & 12. Charissa de Lange. 13–17. Peter Webb. 18 & 19. Bruce Blake. 20 & 21. Peter Webb.

LIFESTYLE

Thomisus blandus, as ambush predators, hide on flowers or other vegetation, patiently waiting for prey. When the opportunity arises, they will pounce on their prey with lightning-fast speed, using their front legs to grasp their target. They have strong bodies, good eyesight, and well-developed tactile sense organs. Numerous images of the species show how the strong front legs that bear rows of strong spines are stretched outwards while on vegetation (Figs 22, 23), waiting for prey. The short hind legs are used to secure their position on the plant. Prey are seized, frequently from the air, when 0.5-1 cm away.

Although they have weak chelicerae, they secrete potent venom, which allows them to attack prey larger than themselves and stop prey from struggling or flying away (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020). Venom very quickly immobilises the prey, allowing them to catch prey up to four times their size (Fig. 24). During SANSA surveys, adults were collected throughout the year.

The males are much smaller than the females (Figs 4,5), and marked sexual dimorphism is also found in shape and colour. The male matures before the female, stops feeding, and then spends all his time searching for females. In some *Thomisus* species, the males are known to sit on a female’s abdomen while awaiting mating, though this behaviour was never observed in *T. blandus*. The female deposits the egg sac covered with layers of silk between the plants (Figs 25, 26).

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Ethiopia, Guinea-Bissau, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Moçambique, Namibia, Somali, South Africa, Sudan, Tanzania, Togo, Zaire, Zambia, Zimbabwe

DISTRIBUTION OF THOMISUS BLANDUS IN SOUTH AFRICA

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SANSA SURVEYS

SOURCE: Specimens sampled during SANSA surveys and housed in Natural History Collections in South Africa. Data was Exported from the SANSA database.

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iNATURALIST

SOURCE: iNaturalist community. Observations of *Thomisus blandus* from South Africa. Exported from <https://www.inaturalist.org> on 17 May 2025.

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Figures 22–26. *Thomisus blandus* female. 22–23. Females waiting for prey. 24. Female feeding on a locust. 25 & 26. Female guarding her egg sac. Credits: 22. Tjeerd de Wit. 23. Alice Rogerson. 24. Richard Gill. 25 & 26. Peter Webb.

CONSERVATION MEASURES

As part of the SANSA we tried to determine where spider species already receive protection. This resulted in surveys in several protected areas resulting in several published checklists that include *T. blandus*. In the SAN parks the species was recorded from Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020); Mountain Zebra National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lotz, 2023); Marakele National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021) and the Garden Route National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024).

Several reserves were also sampled. In the Eastern Cape surveys have been published on the Baviaanskloof Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023); in Gauteng on Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Webb, 2024); in KwaZulu-Natal on Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2006), Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad *et al.*, 2009); in the Limpopo we sampled Makelali Game Reserve (Whitmore *et al.*, 2001), Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2009), Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar *et al.* 2008); and the Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023) in North West and Gondwana Private Game Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Buck, 2023) in the Western Cape.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We would like to thank the following persons who have made their photographs available: Charissa de Lange, Richard Gill, Bruce Blake, Alice Robertson, Tjeerd de Wit and the late Peter Webb. We also thank all the persons that have participated in SANSA surveys and the late Prof Stefan Foord for the SANSA map as well as the photographers that have downloaded their photographs on iNaturalist.

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